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AGRICULTURE

Маккажўхори уруғини экиш учун пневматик экиш аппаратининг асосий параметрлари ва иш режимини мақбуллаштириш

Махамад Тошболтаев, т.ф.д., проф.,

Маркс Хакимов, т.ф.н.,

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The article presents the results of the optimal parameters and operating modes of a pneumatic seeding machine for precise sowing of corn seeds.

В статье приведены результатов оптимальных параметров и режимов работы пневматического высевающего аппарата для точного сева семян кукурузы.

Маккажўхори уруғини пунктир усулда аниқ экишда пневматик экиш аппаратининг мақбул қийматлари ва иш режимини аниқлаш учун кўп омилли экспериментларни математик режалаштириш усулидан фойдаланиб аниқланди [1, 2, 3].

Дастлабки тадқиқотлар натижасида маккажўхори уруғини экиш аниқлиги ва уруғлар орасидаги масофанинг сеяланинг ҳаракат тезлиги (V_c) га, сўрувчи тешиклар диаметри (d) га, уларнинг сони (Z) га ва пневматик экиш аппаратидаги ҳаво сийраклашишига (P) боғлиқ эканлиги аниқланди.

Кўп омилли экспериментларни ўтказишда баҳолаш мезони сифатида экишнинг юқори аниқлиги ва уруғлар орасидаги масофа қабул қилинди.

Тажриба Хартли-4 режаси бўйича аниқланди.

Ўтказилган тажрибалар бўйича олинган маълумотларга ҚХМЭИнинг экспериментларни режалаштириш лабораториясида ишлаб чиқилган “регрессион таҳлиллар” дастурига асосан ишлов берилди [2,3]. Бунда регрессия коэффицентлари қийматини баҳолашда Стьюдент критериясидан, дисперсиянинг бир хиллигини баҳолашда Кохрен критериясидан, регрессион моделларнинг адекватлигини баҳолашда Фишер критериясидан фойдаланилди (1-жадвал)

1-жадвал

Омиллар, уларнинг шартли белгиланиши, вариацияланиш оралиғи ва сатҳи
(уруғларни пунктир усулда экиш учун)

Омилларнинг номланиши	Ўлчов бирлиги	Омилларнинг белгиланиши	Ўзгариш оралиғи	Омиллар сатҳи		
				-1	0	+1
1. Сўрувчи тешиklar диаметри, d	mm	X ₁	1,0	4,0	5,0	6,0
2. Тешиklar сони, Z	dona	X ₂	8	36	44	52
3. Экиш аппаратида ҳаво сийраклашиши, P	mbar	X ₃	10	50	60	70
4. Сеялканинг ҳаракат тезлиги, V _c	m/s	X ₄	0,27	1,67	1,94	2,22

Тажриба натижаларига кўрсатилган тартибда ишлов берилиб, баҳолаш мезонларини адекват тавсифловчи қуйидаги регрессия тенгламалари олинди:

- маккажўхори уруғини экиш аниқлиги (фоиз)

$$Y_1 = 90,939 - 0,750X_1 + 1,417X_2 - 2,607X_4 - 7,419X_1^2 + 1,483X_1X_4 - 5,852X_2^2 + 3,583X_2X_4 - 6,152X_3^2 + 4,700X_3X_4 \quad (1)$$

- уруғлар орасидаги масофа, (cm)

$$Y_2 = 14,014 + 0,101X_1 - 0,082X_2 + 0,402X_4 + 0,362X_1^2 + 0,113X_1X_3 + 0,194X_2^2 - 0,463X_2X_3 - 0,162X_2X_4 + 0,077X_3^2 - 0,106X_3X_4 + 0,310X_4^2 \quad (2)$$

Тадқиқот натижалари бўйича олинган регрессия тенгламалари таҳлилидан кўриниб турибдики, барча омиллар баҳолаш мезонларига сезиларли таъсир кўрсатган.

(1) ва (2) регрессия тенгламалари “Y₁” мезон, яъни маккажўхори уруғини экиш аниқлиги 85 фоиздан кам бўлмаслиги, “Y₂” мезон эса уруғлар орасидаги масофа 14±1 cm бўлиши шартидан келиб чиқиб, сеялканинг ҳаракат тезлиги 1,67-2,22 m/s оралиғида омилларнинг ушбу шартларни бажарилишини таъминловчи қийматлар аниқланди. Олинган натижалар 2-жадвалда келтирилган.

2-жадвал

Пневматик экиш аппарати параметрларининг мақбул қийматлари

V _c (X ₄), m/s		d(X ₁), mm		Z (X ₂), dona		P (X ₃), mbar	
Кодлан-ган	Нагурал, m/s	Кодлан-ган	Нагурал, mm	Кодлан-ган	Нагурал, dona	Кодлан-ган	Нагурал, mbar
1	2,22	0,04940	5,04940	0,42720	47,4	0,3820	63,81
0	1,94	-0,05054	4,94945	0,12107	45,0	-0,0034	59,96
-1	1,67	-0,15049	4,84951	-0,18506	42,5	-0,3820	56,18

Демак, сеялканинг 1,67-2,22 m/s ҳаракат тезликларида маккажўхори уруғларини талаб даражасида экиш аниқлигини ҳамда уруғлар орасидаги масофани таъминлаши учун сўрувчи тешиклар диаметри 4,8-5,0 mm, тешиклар сони 42,5-47,4 dona ва пневматик экиш аппаратида ҳаво сийраклашиши 56,18-63,81 mbar оралиғида бўлиши лозим.

Юқорида келтирилгандан келиб чиқиб, сўрувчи тешиклар диаметри 5,0 mm, уларнинг сони 44 dona ва пневматик экиш аппаратида ҳаво сийраклашишини 60 mbar этиб қабул қиламиз.

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HISTORY

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, violations of governance regulations and problems and shortcomings in the election process in Turkestan.

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Abstract: This article describes the division of the territory of Turkestan into administrative-territorial units, implementation of salov processes in these regions, cases of violation of laws and regulations in the election process.

Key words: Division into administrative-territorial units, implementation of election processes, violations of laws and regulations in election processes, dissatisfaction of the local population with the elections.

According to the "Regulation of 1867", public-economic work was carried out by elected local administration in cities. Cities were divided into parts (city districts), which were ruled by elders. They were elected by the congress of electors appointed in the neighborhoods.

City elders were involved in tax collection and distribution of obligations. They were subordinate to a senior elder who was appointed by the military governor and was in charge of the police service within the city. All lower police officers - mirshabs, mirobs and qazis - were subordinate to the senior elder. All of them were paid from the funds collected from the residents of the city [1. Tilla boev. S. Participation of local population representatives in the administrative management system of the Turkestan region. - T.: Science, 2008].

In 1876, by the order of K. P. Kaufman, the city economic departments were abolished and the city economy was taken under the control of the Russian uezd administration. Only in the cities of Samarkand and New Margilan, such departments were preserved. They were composed of Russian military officials appointed by military governors and representatives of local merchants. The city of Tashkent was considered the political and administrative center of the Turkestan Governorate and had its own administrative system.

Here, the city administration was managed by a special head of the city. Separate public-economic administrations were organized in the "old" and "new" parts of the city, in "Old" Tashkent, the board members were elected by representatives of the upper class of the city, and in the "European" part, leaders were appointed by the military governor of the Syrdarya region.

The activity of public and economic administrations in Tashkent, as in other cities, consisted in carrying out the orders of the city head. In 1876, the City Charter issued on July 16, 1870 was introduced in Tashkent. According to it, the management of the city economy was transferred to the hands of the City Duma. The right to participate in the elections was given to Tashkent residents who are 25 years old, who are Russian citizens, who own real estate, who pay taxes, and whose case is not under court or investigation.

However, "equal self-government" was not in the plan of the colonial authorities. As a result of the city reform, another bureaucratic management mechanism was created, which does not resemble self-management in terms of its formal features. Collecting taxes and monitoring the order in the city - these were the only rights given to the Duma. The executive body of the Tashkent City Duma was the city administration, 2/3 of its members were representatives of the city's Russian population. The mayor of Tashkent was appointed by the administration. He was appointed to the position by the Minister of War on the recommendation of the Governor-General. In the 1970s and early 1980s, this position was usually held by the head of the city of Tashkent. The first Governor-General, K. P. Kaufman, who proposed this procedure, explained it as: "In order to exclude the accidental election of a person who does not meet the requirements for this position, mainly due to the political situation in the city, the majority of whose population consists of recently subdued Muslims." In practice, this city was self-governing, but it was the result of a well-defined and consistent state policy, meaning that it was fully subordinated to the colonial administration.

In accordance with the temporary "Regulation" of 1867 and government decrees, the principle of unified governance over the nomadic and settled peoples of Turkestan was announced, and it was implemented in various forms. In each uezd, the nomadic population was divided into volosts - bolis, and bolis into ovols. Administrative and police power rests with district managers and village elders, who are elected for a three-year term and confirmed by the regional governor.

Administrative and police power for the settled population of the regions was entrusted to elders elected by the population for three years. In order to weaken the rule of the local rich, bolis and avuls were organized according to territorial characteristics rather than clan affiliation. For example, it was determined that a village or ovul consisted of 200 yards or fields, and a bolis consisted of 1,000 to 2,000 yards or fields. This was the reason for the protest and opposition of most of the big rich and clan leaders, who rightly accepted this new order introduced by the government as a legal annulment of the division of Kyrgyz according to the sign of clan affiliation. The colonial administration explained the division of bolis and ovuls according to territorial signs with the need to eliminate "inconveniences in terms of administrative management". K.K. Palen clearly admits that "the unification of a large number of clans under the authority of one clan elder can complicate the task of maintaining peace in the desert" [2. History of military work in Uzbekistan (from the earliest times to the present) // Collective monograph. Responsible editor: D. Ziyaeva. Tashkent, 2012. 79 p].

In order to maintain peace, the rule of clan elders was abolished, and an election system was introduced that allowed new people sympathetic to the tsar's administration to be appointed to the posts of bolis and village heads. Usually, these people were representatives of the rich classes.

The main task of the elected administration was to ensure the successful and timely collection of taxes and fees. Kaufman's report summarizing the results of his 14-year administration in the country notes the important role of these new bodies in the face of russian: Without local-people's management, Kaufman writes, neither the

collection of taxes nor the proper functioning of the newly opened institutions one would hope" the administration in the bolis (Volost) consisted of the bolis administration and the bolis congress of elected representatives. The elections of the head of the bolis were two-level, first a village meeting was held and one representative was elected from 50 households. Then the representatives elected from the village gatherings gathered at the bolis congress, which was held with the participation of Russian officials. Usually, these were the head of the uezd or his assistant, who did not interfere in the work of the congress, but controlled the order. Before the congress started, the presence of fifty heads was checked. If less than 2/3 of the number of elected representatives gathered at the congress, the divisional congress was canceled.

Election of the head of the district, people's judges and their candidates to the congress of the district; setting salaries for officials of lower administrations; inspections, roads, control of the condition of farm equipment; was given the right to use water and manage water supply works.

In addition to economic affairs, the manager of the bolis also performed police functions: he controlled the internal peace of the bolis, conducted investigations on crimes tried in the people's court, brought to the attention of the population all the laws and orders of the colonial administration [3. Shoniyozov, K. (2001). The process of formation of the Uzbek people. Tashkent.].

In agreement with the head of the uezd, the bolis administrator for public affairs could call and disperse the bolis congress, guard the order in it, monitor the actions of the village and village elders. If for some reason the Russian administration was not satisfied with the person of the head of the bolis, the military governor of the region could call a new election or replace his head with another person at his discretion.

The tsar's administration made extensive use of this right. For example, F.K. Girs provides the following information in his report on the inspection of the activities of the bolis and village administrations: "Out of 109 bolis administrators in Syrdarya

region, 38 people were dismissed within three years., which is 35% or about 13 cases per year. Such information can be given for other regions of Turkestan.

Officials working in lower administrations often abused their positions. There are many facts that indicate that they were engaged in bribery, collecting illegal fees, embezzling taxes collected from the population, and taking revenge on people they did not like. Bolis manager and elder positions often attracted crooked people. Elections to district and village administrations are often fiercely fought between different groups trying to get their candidates for them.

"The attempt to occupy the seat of the head of the district," writes F.K. Girs in his report, "is explained by the fact that, on the one hand, the amount of salary is deceptively large, and on the other hand, he is given the right to collect taxes in the entire district, and he collects illegal fees." can collect very easily, deposit collected money late to the treasury and sometimes even hide it. In addition, according to the right granted to him (Article 112 of the "Regulation" of 1867), the manager of the division may impose a fine of up to 3 soums. It is absolutely impossible to control his activities in this regard, especially in places where the nomadic population lives." According to the "Regulation" of 1867, a new system of tax collection was introduced, which was based on the calculation of the types of occupations and incomes of the population. A general levy was introduced for the nomadic population, and it was set at 2 rubles 75 tinyas for each levy. The land tax equal to 1/10 of the harvest for the settled population is khiroj, sales tax. He paid zakat and taxes for maintenance of irrigation canals, roads, bridges, markets, etc. Taxes were distributed among village communities by the Bolis Congress. Most of the taxes fell on the poor. Bolis managers and village tax collectors were essentially exempted from paying taxes. Thus, in the mid-1960s and mid-1980s, the administrative apparatus consisted of a system of closely related main elements of the administrative mechanism and bodies that acted in the interests of russian and its colonial policy. The peculiar aspect of this apparatus is its excessive bureaucratic centralization, which is reflected in the fact that the functions of law creation, issuing

orders, execution and control are concentrated in its hands. At the same time, some of the functions of the administrative apparatus were assigned to the institutions of local authority, which operated under the control of the Russian authorities - elders and district administrations. Such "compromise" in the system of colonial power was caused by the military situation, the need to achieve stability and ease the burden of performing colonial tasks. Such a tactical approach to the problem of managing Turkestan was required by the experience gained in other regions of the empire and an attempt to achieve the goals of turning the region into its own colony faster and more successfully.

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Medieval caravanserais of Ustyurt

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Abstract: In the advanced Middle Ages, the ancient caravan routes from Khorezm through Ustyurt to the Volga continued to be used. In the Middle Ages, a number of roadside structures - rabots, caravanserais - were built in this direction, which show the importance of the South Aral Bay in international political, economic and cultural relations.

Keywords: The Late Middle Ages, the Great Silk Road, Khorezm, Ustyurt, Koshbulok caravanserai, trade routes, rabots, caravanserai, wells, the medieval caravan routes.

On the caravan route from Khorezm to the Volga through Ustyurt, a number of medieval caravanserais have been explored. Their location plays an important role in clarifying the routes of the caravan routes that passed from the Khorezm capital Urganch (Old Urganch. - K.S.) through Ustyurt to the Volga region and Eastern Europe in the Middle Ages.

In the late Middle Ages, caravan routes passed from Khorezm to the Volga region in two directions. The first route went from Urganch, the capital of Khorezm, through Zanzhan Rabat and the village of Habab, and ascended to Ustyurt through Karaumbet Pass. This road that passed through Ustyurt led to the banks of the Emba river through the steppe road and from here to the Volga region. From here, the road branched off, one led to the country of the Khazars, and the other led to the Bulgar kingdom. In the sources, Zanzhan rabot located in this direction is recorded as "Bab at-turk" - "Gate of the Turks" [1].

The second route from Khorezm to the Volga region went west through the Kashkajol pass in Ustyurt, through Borsa kelmas to Mangqishlaq, and from there to the Caspian Sea (map 000).

A number of fortified caravanserais were found and studied on the caravan route connecting the capital of Khorezm with the Volga region through Ustyurt. One of

them is 45 km from Karaumbet Pass. Uchkuduq Caravanserai is located in the north-west. During the research, it was found that there were wells near this caravanserai. According to material sources, this caravanserai was widely used during the period when Western Khorezm was part of the Golden Horde state, in the XIII-XIV centuries [2].

Koshbulok caravanserai. This caravanserai was discovered 35 km away from the Bulok caravanserai in Ustyurt. Based on the analysis of material findings and ceramics, it is known that this caravanserai also belongs to the XIII-XIV centuries. Khorezm was divided into two parts as a result of Genghis Khan's invasion, the lands on the right bank of the Amudarya were included in the Chigotoy ulus, and the left bank lands were included in the Joji ulus. By the second half of the 13th century, economic life was restored in the South Aral Sea region, which was part of the Golden Horde state, and internal and external trade relations began to revive. In this, the policy of the Mongolian rulers on the restoration of destroyed cities, development of agriculture, handicrafts, and trade took the main place.

In the first half of the 13th century, according to the Arab geographer Yaqut, not only the caravan routes from Khorezm to the Volga region, which were used in earlier times, but also the Caspian waterway through Mangiqishlaq were used [3].

According to the information given by Ibn Arabshah, the trade caravans that left Khorezm reached the Crimea without any guides, with the possibility of changing horses, food and safety. It is important that these data are also shown by the results of archaeological research [5].

In the Late Middle Ages, the trade caravans that set off from Urganch, the capital of Khorezm, towards the Volga region, came to Koshkuduk through the eastern part of the sand dunes of Uchkuduk, Bulok, Koshbulok, Beleuli, Churuk, Koshi, Sam in Ustyurt. From here, passing through Minsu almady, it descended from Ustyurt and came to Saraychik along the route of Uchkan, Bokachi, Kaynar, Tas-kichu, Blavli. A number of researches have been conducted to determine the landing places of trade caravans passing through Ustyurt. In 1865, the Russian officer L. Mayer also

paid attention to this issue during the preparation of "Materials on Russian Geography and Statistics". According to him, the most convenient way from Ustyurt is near Chumishtikol, where there were five old descent trails [6]. The Tas-astav well, found on the eastern shore of Chumishtikol, also provides information about this route through Ustyurt [7].

In Ustyurt, according to the conducted studies, there are two horizons of water layers under the ground, and fresh water reserves are located in their upper layer [8]. These water reserves provide water to springs and wells dug by residents in Ustyurt, and play a key role in the formation and development of the anthropogenic landscape in the region, and in the quality of life. The sandy areas in the north-west and central part of Ustyurt are also rich in fresh water reserves, and deep wells such as Barak, Tasquduq, Karamulla, Asmantai-matay have been found [9]. They played an important role in the activity of the caravan routes that passed through Ustyurt in ancient times and the Middle Ages.

It should be noted that the studied monuments are located along the medieval caravan routes that passed through the fortified Ustyurt. These results indicate, on the one hand, that the routes of communication and trade routes founded in ancient times were also used in the Middle Ages, and on the other hand, that the places in Ustyurt were formed and developed in connection with the activity of caravan routes.

Conclusions:

1. There is a lot of information about the medieval caravan routes from Urganch to the Volga region through Ustyurt in the written sources of the 10th-11th centuries.
2. In the 12th-13th centuries, the Urganch-Ustyurt-Saray route was considered the busiest and internationally important caravan route of the Great Silk Road. Due to the importance of this trade route during the Anushtegin rulers of Khorezm, many rabots, caravanserais, and wells were built.

3. In the 13th-14th centuries, this route continued to be actively used, and new roadside structures were built, which played an important role in the development of caravan trade.

4. This trade route continued to be used in the 15th-19th centuries, and in the sources this route was known as the "Khiva Road".

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MEDICINE

Clinical and instrumental features of the course of Takayasu's disease in children.

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Aortoarteritis in children (Takayasu's disease), or pulseless disease, is an inflammation of large vessels. In Asian countries (in particular, India), cases of aortoarteritis in children are common. However, this disease affects children of all ethnic groups and worldwide ranks 3rd among childhood vasculitis after hemorrhagic vasculitis and Kawasaki disease.

The purpose of the study was to evaluate the clinical and instrumental features of the course of aortoarteritis in children.

Material and methods. Under observation were 6 girls who were hospitalized in the TMA clinic with a diagnosis of aortoarteritis from 2019 to 2022. The age of the girls was 11-18 years, the duration of the disease ranged from 6 months to 3 years. All patients were rural residents.

Results. Clinical manifestations of aortoarteritis were characterized by night sweats 75%, loss of appetite 75% and body weight 75%, fatigue 75%, myalgia 50% and inflammation of the joints 50%, arterial hypertension 100%. A history of erythema nodosum 50%, butterfly erythema 50%, and vasculitis nodosum 50%, myopericarditis 50%, rheumatoid arthritis 25%, and polymyositis 25% were observed. Against the background of the disappearance of the pulse on the hands, a characteristic noise was observed over the carotid and subclavian arteries. When interpreting laboratory tests, an increase in antistreptolysin O, C-reactive protein, titer of anti-CCP-14ED/ml, ANA-1:100 was observed in all patients. On echocardiography, sealing of the aortic valves 30%, mitral valve 25%. Hypertrophy of the myocardium of the left ventricle 60% and an increase in the cavity of the left atrium and ventricle -50%. Among the instrumental methods for diagnosing vascular lesions in Takayasu's arteritis, one of the leading places belongs to multislice contrast tomography of the arteries. It allows you to assess the degree of

hemodynamic disturbances as well as the state of the arterial wall. In all cases of MSCT interpretations, we visualized a pronounced edema of the vascular wall, the disappearance of visualization of large arteries of varying degrees, which significantly correlated with the clinical and laboratory picture of the disease.

Conclusions. In the diagnosis of aortoarteritis, general clinical tests play a key role, but only with the help of instrumental diagnostic methods can a final conclusion be made. MSCT in order to assess hemodynamic disorders and the state of the vascular wall is supposedly an informative minimally invasive method for visualizing stenotic and inflammatory changes in the aorta and its main branches.

MSCT can be used to both diagnose and monitor Takayasu's arteritis. A combination of different imaging modalities may be recommended to increase the value of vascular assessment, especially in patients with long-standing Takayasu's arteritis or an atypical presentation of the disease.

Results of the use of chemoben in the surgical treatment of parenchymatous bleeding

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Relevance. One of the important directions in the development of healthcare is not only the introduction of advanced medical technologies, but also the development of domestic medical products for various purposes with the aim of "import substitution". For practical surgery, in this regard, the introduction of domestic versions of wound dressings is of particular importance, since foreign analogues are characterized by high cost and, therefore, cannot be widely used in our country. The first successful development of a domestic hemostatic coating (Geprocel) has already been tested in many clinics, and its effectiveness has been proven in several scientific studies. Developments in this direction were continued and a new version of the hemostatic coating was created on the basis of the primary agent, the properties of which included not only the hemostatic effect, but also the possibility of anti-adhesion activity. The experimental and morphological studies carried out made it possible to substantiate the effectiveness of the use of a new domestic hemostatic implant Hemoben in parenchymal bleeding. This served as the basis for the introduction of a new tool in clinical practice.

Materials and methods: The main group included 10 patients with injuries of the liver or spleen, in whom Hemoben was used intraoperatively to achieve hemostasis. The comparison group included 26 patients selected for similar signs of damage to the liver or spleen; intraoperative hemostasis was achieved by coagulation, temporary wound plugging and (or) stitching. In all cases, attempts were made to perform organ-preserving operations, coagulation of damaged areas of the spleen and liver, in some cases, suturing of tears of the liver capsule, a combination of these manipulations with fixation of the omentum to ensure more reliable hemostasis.

If we consider the nature of the operations performed separately by organs and groups, it becomes obvious that adequate hemostasis was achieved in the main group with spleen injuries in 100% (4 patients), with liver injuries in 83.3% (5 patients). While in the comparison group these figures were 77.8% (7 patients) and 64.7% (11 patients), respectively. Moreover, if in the main group splenectomy was not performed in any case, in the comparison group in 2 (22.2%) cases there was a relapse of bleeding, which led to an expansion of the intervention and splenectomy. With liver injuries in the main group, in 1 (16.7%) case there was repeated bleeding, as a result, additional stitching of the liver wound was required. In the control group, the result is much worse, in 6 (35.3%) cases there was a recurrence of bleeding, which required additional suturing of the liver wound. Thus, if in the main group adequate primary hemostasis was achieved in 90% of cases (9 out of 10 patients), in the control group this figure was only 69.2% (18 out of 26 patients).

Results: It took an average of 18.5 ± 3.4 minutes to achieve hemostasis in the main group, while in the control group it took 1.5 times more - 28.1 ± 14.8 minutes ($t = 3.09$; $p < 0.05$). Accordingly, this affected the time of the operation, if in the main group the entire intervention took 57 ± 11.4 minutes, in the control group it took 72.9 ± 21.9 minutes ($t = 2.84$; $p < 0.05$). Achieving thorough hemostasis affected the further postoperative course. In particular, the drainage discharge in the control group on the 1st-2nd-3rd day exceeded that in the main group. On the first day, 59.4 ± 27.7 ml versus 38.5 ± 12.0 ml ($t = 3.15$; $p < 0.05$). On the second day 42.7 ± 20.1 ml versus 26.0 ± 9.4 ml ($t = 3.39$; $p < 0.05$). On the third day, 27.1 ± 16.1 ml versus 14.5 ± 5.0 ml, respectively ($t = 3.57$; $p < 0.05$).

Sometimes the nature of the discharge means more than its quantity. Therefore, in order to accurately determine the comparability of the fluid released from the abdominal cavity, we determined the level of hemoglobin in the exudate obtained from the drains. On the first day, the level of hemoglobin in the discharge from the drainage in the control group was 22.6 ± 8.4 g/l, while in the main group this figure was 14.4 ± 5.3 g/l ($t = 3.51$; $p < 0.05$). On the second day 19.8 ± 9.2 g/l versus 12.5 ± 3.9

g/l ($t = 3.36$; $p < 0.05$). On the third day, 15.1 ± 6.9 g/l versus 9.7 ± 2.2 g/l, respectively ($t = 3.56$; $p < 0.05$).

Everyone knows that the presence of a large discharge with intense hemorrhagic coloration requires a longer period of drainage, and, accordingly, hospitalization. Due to the fact that in the control group the amount of discharge from the drainage was large, and the nature of the fluid was more hemorrhagic, the drainage time was longer than in the main group. Thus, in the control group, the drains functioned for an average of 6.2 ± 2.4 days, while in the main group this figure was 4.2 ± 1.7 days ($t = 2.85$; $p < 0.05$). The duration of hospitalization was 8.4 ± 1.9 days in the control group versus 6.4 ± 1.3 g/l in the main group ($t = 3.47$; $p < 0.05$).

In the main group, intraoperative hemostasis was significantly more reliable, which affected the amount and nature of discharge from the drains in the early postoperative period. As a result, the drains were removed earlier than in the control group, and the patients were discharged from the hospital earlier. Acceleration of the period of achieving absolute hemostasis from 28.1 ± 18.5 to 18.5 ± 3.4 minutes ($t = 3.09$; $p < 0.05$) made it possible to reduce the operation time from 72.9 ± 21.9 minutes in the group comparisons up to 57.0 ± 11.4 minutes in the main group ($t = 2.84$; $p < 0.05$).

In the immediate period after the operation, a significantly lower amount of drainage discharge was noted in the main group - 38.5 ± 12.0 ml versus 59.4 ± 27.7 ml in the comparison group on the first day ($t = 3.15$; $p < 0, 05$) and on the third day 14.5 ± 5.0 ml versus 27.1 ± 16.1 ml ($t = 3.57$; $p < 0.05$). The good hemostatic effect of Hemoben also ensured a significantly low hemoglobin content in the discharge through the drains, which was 14.4 ± 5.3 g/l versus 22.6 ± 8.4 g/l on the first day ($t = 3.51$; $p < 0.05$) and on the third day 9.7 ± 2.2 g/l versus 15.1 ± 6.9 g/l ($t = 3.56$; $p < 0.05$).

In general, there was a reduction in the period of drainage of the abdominal cavity from 6.2 ± 2.4 days in the comparison group to 4.2 ± 1.7 days in the main group ($t = 2.85$; $p < 0.05$) and the total period of hospital treatment from 8.4 ± 1.9 days to 6.4 ± 1.3 days ($t = 3.47$; $p < 0.05$).

Conclusions: The introduction of a new domestic Hemoben implant into clinical practice made it possible to positively characterize the prospects for its use to stop parenchymal bleeding, so in the intraoperative period, the effectiveness of primary hemostasis with limited injuries of the liver or spleen was 90% versus 69.2% in the comparison group, where, respectively, in 30 .8% of cases required additional measures.

Оценка клинических характеристик острого синусита, сопровождающегося аллергическим ринитом у детей

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Актуальность. Аллергический ринит (АР) - хроническое заболевание полости носа, патогенезом которого является 1 E - опосредованное воспаление слизистой оболочки носа. АР определяется у 10-20% детского населения [4]. У детей ар приводит к различным ограничениям в активности, снижению качества физических, психологических и социальных аспектов жизни [2].

Таким образом, актуально искать альтернативные методы исследования ОНП, которые отвечают требованиям отоларингологов и могут быть использованы не только для диагностики, но и в процессе динамического наблюдения за заболеванием [1,3].

Метод должен быть информативным и безопасным. К таким методам относится двумерное ультразвуковое исследование (УЗИ), но способ его использования в диагностике гайморита у детей не разработан.

Цель исследования. Целью исследования является изучение клинических и экспериментальных особенностей острого синусита у детей с ар с целью повышения эффективности лечения данной патологии.

Материалы и методы исследования. Для решения поставленную перед нами задачу, мы провели обследования в общей сложности 75 детей, поступивших в отделение оториноларингологии с острым синуситом. С целью повышения эффективности лечения у них мы изучили клинические и экспериментальные особенности острого синусита у детей с аллергическим ринитом.

Результаты исследования. Время мукоцилиарного транспорта и двигательная активность мерцательного эпителия слизистой оболочки полости носа у здоровых детей не имеет возрастных и половых различий. В норме время сахаринового теста у детей составляет $7,54 \pm 0,34$ мин. Частота биения ресничек в разных анатомических зонах полости носа в детском

возрасте различна и равна на нижней носовой раковине $3,19 \pm 1,71$ Гц, на средней носовой раковине - $6,95 \pm 2,36$ Гц ($p < 0,001$).

При остром гнойном синусите у детей наблюдается достоверное удлинение времени сахаринового теста до $10,84 \pm 0,49$ мин. и снижение двигательной активности цилиарного аппарата слизистой оболочки полости носа до $0,34 \pm 0,26$ Гц на нижней носовой раковине и $3,42 \pm 2,17$ Гц на средней носовой раковине.

По мере роста ребенка отмечается изменение основных показателей носового дыхания в виде нарастания суммарного объемного потока и уменьшения носового сопротивления, при этом значимые половые различия отсутствуют. Наиболее существенная динамика дыхательной функции полости носа у детей приходится на период младшего школьного (7-10 лет) и подросткового возраста (15-17 лет).

Носовой цикл присутствует у 95% здоровых детей и у 66,7% детей, больных синуситами. В детском возрасте доминирует неклассический носовой цикл. При воспалительных процессах в околоносовых пазухах периодичность флюктуаций короче, чем в норме, однако сохраняется их видовая принадлежность, что позволяет рассматривать носовой цикл как стойкий физиологический феномен, отражающий реактивность слизистой оболочки полости носа.

Отрицательное давление, создаваемое в полости носа во время ЯМИК-процедуры, не оказывает существенного влияния на функциональное состояние полости носа. После применения синус-катетера не наблюдается стойкого угнетения мукоцилиарного транспорта и двигательной активности мерцательного эпителия, что может служить доказательством безопасности ЯМИК-метода.

Вывод. Для оценки результатов лечения детей с синуситами рекомендуется использовать двухмерную ультрасонографию как безопасный и информативный метод исследования. Критерием санации околоносовых пазух

на ультразвуковых сканограммах служит отсутствие каких-либо экзогенных сигналов в проекции синусов.

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PHILOLOGY

Qadimgi davr ingliz adabiyotida “suv” konsepti

(Beowulf misolida)

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada kognitiv lingvistika nazariyasidan kelib chiqqan holda metaforalar tavsifi va ularning madaniyat bilan uzviy bog’liqligi haqida fikr yuritilgan. Shuningdek, “suv” konsepti va ularning metafora sifatida “Beowulf” da qo’llanishi ko’rib chiqilgan. Metaforalar yordamida “suv” konseptining ma’nolari isbotlab berilgan.

Annotation. Beowulf is a heroic poem, considered the highest achievement of Old English literature and the earliest European vernacular epic. It deals with events of the early 6th century CE and is believed to have been composed between 700 and 750.

One of the salient characteristics is the application of metaphorical language. As the language tool and main thread of the novel, metaphors not only strengthen the artistic effects of the work, but also contribute significantly to the exploration of its deep themes and dense implications. Based on Conceptual Metaphor put forward by Lakoff & Johnson, the thesis aims to analyze the metaphors of the novel and the metaphorical meanings of the governing image of water.

Keywords: conceptual metaphor, water metaphors, Beowulf

1. Kirish.

“**Beowulf**” qahramonlik dostoni sanalib, qadimgi ingliz tilida 8-10-asrlar oraliq’ida yozilgan va muallifi ma’lum emas. Bu mumtoz qo’lyozma anglo-saksonlar adabiyotining nodir namunasi hisoblanib, ilm, nazariya va munozaralar kabi masalalar mavzu sifatida yoritilgan. Asarning voqeasi qahramon Beowulf va uning dushmani Grendal hamda Grendalning onasi bilan murosasizlar janglari haqida

bayon qilingan. Lekin, asarning asosiy mavzusi yaxshilik va yomonlik o'rtasidagi jang haqida muhohasa yuritadi. Ular Beowulf va Grendal timsoli orqali beriladi.

Beowulfda ko'plab metaforalarni uchratish mumkin. Konseptual metafora nazariyasidan kelib chiqqan "suv" bilan bog'liq tushunchalar haqida quyida batafsil to'xtalib o'tilsa-da, Beowulfda qo'llangan metaforalarning umumiy turlari haqida eslatib o'tish ham maqsadga muvofiqdir. Asarning aksar qismlarida yaxshilik va yomonlik muqoyasa qilingan metaforalar ko'p uchraydi. Xususan:

"Beowulf's metaphors show him to be all goodness and light, coming to protect his people. He is like God in a way, through metaphors such as he is "the shepherd of the land." And Grendel is evil incarnate, he is almost like the devil or a demon, being called "the Lord's outcast" among many other evil-related things¹", Beowulfga qarata qo'llanilgan metaforalar uning yaxshilik va yorug'lik ramzi ekanini va odamlarni himoya qilish uchun kelganini ko'rsatish va oson tushuntirish maqsadida foydalanilgan. U, xuddiki, xudoga o'xshaydi ya'ni metafora bilan izohlansa, u yerning cho'ponidir deyilgan, Grendal esa "Xudoning tashlandig'I yoki jamiyatdan ajratilgan" shaklida gavydalantirilgan.

2. Konseptual metafora nazariyasi.

Metafora qadimgi asrlardan buyon foydalanib kelgan va qiymatga ega bo'lgan til birligidir. Aristotel metaforaga shunday ta'rif beradi: "the greatest thing, by far, is to be a master of metaphor. It is the one thing that cannot be learnt and it is also, sign of genius..." (Kittay, 1989, p.1) ya'ni, metaforani qo'llay olish eng buyuk ish va oxiriga qadar o'rganib bo'lmaydigan birlikdir va oqillikning belgisidir. Metaforalar, shuningdek, mashhur grek yozuvchilari Sofokl va Yevriped asarlarida ham uchraydi.

Metafora so'zining negiziga e'tibor beradigan bo'lsak, grek tilidan olingan bo'lib, "meta" "ko'chirmoq" va "pherein" ingliz tiliga tarjima qilinganda "to bear" ya'ni "olib yurmoq" ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Metaforalarning qo'llanilish doirasi juda ham keng bo'lib, avvallari asosan adabiy birlik sifatida, she'riyat va ritorikada eng asosiy

¹ <https://www.ancient-literature.com/metaphors-in-beowulf>

unsur sifatida qaralgan bo'lsa-da, Lakoff va Johnson (1980) ning nazariyasidan keyin metaforalar nafaqat adabiyotning balki til hamda konseptning ham asosiy birligi sifatida ko'riya boshladi.

Lakoff va Johnson (1980) ning mashhur “Metaphors we live by” asari metaforaga bo'lgan munosabatni qaytadan yuzaga keltirdi va ko'pchilik tadqiqotchilarda qiziqish uyg'otdi. Ularning fikricha: “Metaphor is pervasive in everyday life, not just in language but in thought and action; our ordinary conceptual system, in terms of which we both think and act, is fundamentally metaphorical in nature.” (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980). Shuningdek, ular bu kitobda til va metaforaning tabiati hamda bir qator misollar orqali metaforalarning kognitiv tuzulishi va til o'rtasidagi yaqin aloqadorlikni tahlil qilishadi. Xususan quyidagi metaforalarni konseptual metafora sifatida ko'rsatadi:

- a) Time is money – Vaqt – puldir
- b) Life is journey – Hayot – sayohatdir
- c) Life is play – Hayot-o'yindir
- d) Argument is war – Bahs-urushdir.

Metaforaning kognitiv va konseptual asosga egaligi va insonlarning tajribasi asosida yuzaga kelishi aytilayotgan bo'lsa-da, bunga e'tiroz bildiruvchi tadqiqotchilar ham topiladi.

Metaforalar kundalik hayotda qo'llanuvchi til va konseptual birlik ekanligidan kelib chiqadigan bo'lsak, metaforalar insonlarning ong jarayoni bilan bog'liq hodisadir. Ushbu maqolada “suv” konseptining ma'nolari, “suv” bilan bog'liq metaforalarning ingliz adabiyoti, xususan, “Beowulf” da ishlatilishiga doir masalalar ko'rib chiqilgan.

3. Adabiyot va “suv” konsepti

“Suv” konsepti adabiyotda hissiyot, ichki kechinmalar va aks ta'sirlarning ramzi sifatida tasvirlanadi. Suv konsepti adabiy asarlarda o'zgaruvchanlik va go'zallik, yordamchi va buzg'unchi kabi ma'nolarda qo'llanilib, ba'zan tug'ilish va o'limni, ba'zan esa sokinlik, bosiqlik va ayni damda shafqatsizlikni ifodalab kelgan.

Adabiy asarlarda, suv xotirjamlik, go'zallik va o'zgaruvchanlik demakdir. Shuningdek, u ayrim o'rinlarda doimiy bo'hronlari orqali kuch ishlatib boshqaruvchi sifatida ham talqin etilgan. Suvning turlariga ko'ra turli ma'nolarda ham ishlatilgan. Masalan, tez o'zanli suv oqimi kuch va e'tibor ramzi sifatida qaralgan va yana adabiy asarlarda daryo, asosan, qayta tug'ilish va da'volash metaforasi o'rnida qo'llangan².

Ingliz tilida quyidagicha metaforalarni uchratish mumkin:

- The river is a weaving snake- Daryo- to'lg'onuvchi ilondir.
- The water searched for the sea – Suv- qidirilayotgan ummondir
- The water roared- Suv – na'radir.

Ushbu metaforalardan anglashiladiki, suv konsepti adabiy asarlarda o'ndan ortiq ma'nolarda qo'llaniladi. Hareshwar Roy (2018) ga ko'ra, hindlarning muqaddas kitoblarida tushuntirilishicha, yerdagi hayot dengizning paydo bo'lishidan boshlangan va demakki dastlabki hayot suvda mavjud bo'lgan. Shu bois ham butun bir katta koinot suvdan iborat va usiz mavjud emas. Leonardo da Vinci nazariyasiga ko'ra esa, "Water is the driving force in nature", suv tabiatni boshqaruvchi kuchdir. Thoreau esa 'Life in us is like the water in a river'³, ya'ni bizning hayot daryodagi suv yanglig'dir, deb yozadi. "Suv" konsepti hamma davrlarda ham insonlarni qiziqtirib kelgan. Adabiyotda suv, xususan, dengiz bizning orzuyimiz, istaklarimiz va qo'rquvimiz metaforasidir. Vilyam Shekspirning nodir dramalaridan biri "The Tempest" da quyidagicha parchani uchratish mumkin:

'Full fathom five thy father lies;
Of his bones are coral made;
Those are pearls that were his eyes:
Nothing of him that doth fade,
But doth suffer a sea-change
Into something rich and strange.

² Gengqing Chen¹ & Weiwei Wang, "Metaphorical Analysis of the Image of Water in Beloved", Qinhuangdao Branch of Northeast Petroleum University, Qinhuangdao, China

³ Hareshwar Roy, Water and literature, Scientific journal, 2018

Sea-nymphs hourly ring his knell: Ding-dong

Hark! now I hear them, —Ding-dong, bell.’ Demakki, dengiz inson tomonidan o’zgartirilib, azoblanuvchi obraz sifatida gavdalangan bo’lsa, “The Tide Rises”da suv vaqt, hech qachon tugamaydigan va o’zgarmaydigan ramz sifatida talqin qilinadi.

4. “Suv” konsepti va Beowulf

“Beowulf” asarida “suv” tasvirining metaforik tahlili va uning ma’nolari ko’rib chiqilganda ma’lum bo’ldiki, metaforalar tabiatdan va o’sha davr odamlarining hayotidan olingan. Maqolaning ushbu qismida suv bilan bog’liq metaforalar ma’nolari va bu metaforalarning psixologik, diniy va madaniy asoslari tahlil qilingan bo’lib, ingliz madaniyati va e’tiqodiga ko’ra suv insonlar o’rtasidagi bog’lovchi vosita ekanligi aytilgan. Oksford ingliz tili lug’atiga ko’ra, suv har qanday, rangsiz, ta’msiz, toza suyuqlikni ifodalaydi. Ilmiy jihatdan suv yer va bizning hayotimizning muhim elementidir. Badiiy adabiyotda esa, u hamisha qudrat, qayta tug’ilish va vayronagarchilik metaforalari bilan yonma yon qo’yilgan.

Masalan, “Beowulf” da quyidagi jummalarni uchratish mumkin:

1) Then they bore him over to ocean’s billow, loving clansmen, as late he charged them, while wielded words the winsome Scyld, the leader beloved who long had ruled⁴.

Keyin, ular uni okeanning ulkan to’lqinlari uzra ko’rishdi, sevimli qabiladoshlari (keyinchalik ularga bosh bo’ladi) ga qarata donishmand Scyld so’zlarini aytganida, ular uzoq hukmronlik qiladigan boshliqlarini xush ko’rishdi.

Ushbu o’rinda ulkan dengiz to’lqini, mas’uliyat, donishmandlik va boshqaruvchilik so’zlari bilan ketma-ketlikda qo’llangan bo’lib, Beowulfning hukmronligi va donishmandligi, dengiz kabi o’zgarmas va mas’uliyatli ekanligiga ishora qilingan. Ya’ni inson-okean metaforasi, yoinki, yuqorida keltirib o’tganimiz, bizdagi hayot – daryodagi suvdir shaklidan biroz boshqacha qo’llanilib, okeanga muqoyasa qilingan hukmdorning qudrati ko’rsatib o’tilgan.

⁴ Beowulfdan olingan parcha 119-bet

2) No ship have I known so nobly dight with weapons of war and weeds of battle, with breastplate and blade: on his bosom lay a heaped hoard that hence should go far o'er the flood with him floating away.

Ushbu o'rinda "float" so'zi ham asl ma'nosida va ko'chma ma'noda metafora sifatida qo'llanilgan. Beowulfning shijoatini o'ziga sig'mayotgan, jo'shib chiqayotgan ulkan dengiz mavjlariga o'xshatilgan.

3) Then moved o'er the waters by might of the wind that bark like a bird with breast of foam, till in season due, on the second day, the curved prow such course had run that sailors now could see the land, sea-cliffs shining, steep high hills, headlands broad.

Bu yerda ifodalangan "sea-cliff" so'zi dengiz ma'nosini ifodalamas-da, dengizga tutash qoyalarning nur taratishi haqida fikr bildirilgan, ushbu o'rinda to'rt unurning qo'llanishiga guvoh bo'lishimiz mumkin.

Xulosa o'rnida aytilsa, suv adabiyotning ajralmas va asosiy bo'g'inidir. Yuqorida ko'rsatib o'tilgan misollardan anglash mumkinki, suv badiiy asarlarda qudrat, o'zgaruvchanlik va o'tkinchilik ma'nolarida ham qo'llaniladi.

5. Xulosa

Beowulf ingliz adabiyotining qadimgi va yuksak namunasi sifatida, o'sha davr hayoti, madaniyati va insonlarning diniy qarashlarini ochib bergan asardir. Asarda yaxshilik va yomonlik kurashini insonlar orqali bayon qila turib, muallif ko'plab metaforalarga urg'u beradi va yaxshilik tomonida hamisha "suv" konseptini ilgari suradi. Janglarda va qiyinchilik paytlarda Beowulf hamda okean tasviri hamisha yelkama-yelka qo'yiladi yoki Beowulfning shiddati dengiz to'lqinlari shijoati bilan bayon qilinadi. Asardan xulosa qilish mumkinki, muallif ingliz adabiyotining ajralmas bo'lagi sifatida suv konseptini tasvirlaydi va uni asosiy maqsadni yetkazuvchi vosita sifatida foydalanadi.

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International human rights and gender equality

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ABSTRACT

In September 2019, Uzbekistan passed the country's first law on gender equality, "Securing equal rights and opportunities for women and men". The long-awaited act represents a strong stand against gender discrimination and ensures equal rights for both sexes – an ambitious goal in a society characterized by prejudices against gender identity world is ingrained. Although the Constitution guarantees equal rights, opportunities for men and women are not equal. For example, women make up only 16% of Oliy Majlis' Legislative Chamber (Parliament). Additionally, women are underrepresented in leadership positions, especially in government, and have limited ability to own property or start businesses. Although there are no current legal constraints, women also play a secondary role in the fields of science, research and engineering, such as computer science and engineering. Women and girls represent half of the world's population and therefore also half of its potential. Gender equality, in addition to being a fundamental human right, is essential to achieving peaceful societies, endowed with all human potential, and sustainable development. Additionally, women's empowerment has been shown to boost productivity and economic growth. Unfortunately, there is still a long way to go to achieve full equality of rights and opportunities between men and women, UN Women warns. It is therefore paramount to end many forms of gender-based violence and to ensure equal access to quality education and health, economic resources and political participation for women and girls and men and boys. It is also essential to achieve equal opportunities in access to employment and management and decision-making positions at all levels.

Key words: gender equality, political participation, women and girls, leadership positions, human rights, equality, fundamental human right, empower all women, women's rights, leadership opportunities.

As you know, according to United Nations General Assembly Resolution 70 on Sustainable Development, adopted in September 2015, the Republic of Uzbekistan intends to organize systematic work on the consistent implementation of the Chapter on Sustainable Development. the United Nations global agenda for sustainable development to 2030. The Cabinet of Ministers adopted a resolution “On Measures for the Implementation of National Goals and Targets in the Area of Sustainable Development” by 2030”. At the same time, in the fifth Sustainable Development Goal, Uzbekistan sets out nine goals to ensure gender equality and empower all women. According to the goals of Goal 5 (Gender Equality), by 2030, all forms of discrimination against all women should be eliminated, ensuring the full and effective participation of women at all levels. all levels of political, economic and social decision making and leadership opportunities. In addition, this objective includes the introduction of gender equality principles in the adoption of state programs at different levels of government. In recent years, many areas have been implemented to ensure gender equality and enhance the role of women in political and social life: • Improve legislation on women's rights; • Improve the institutional framework for women's protection; • Raise community awareness on gender equality and women's rights; • Train law enforcement officers, in accordance with applicable law. Uzbekistan has passed a number of laws, including presidential decrees and decrees on women's rights, including on gender equality and the protection of women from violence and oppression, as well as enhancing the status of women. position of female entrepreneurs. From a gender equality perspective, positive changes in education should be noted. In other words, since 2017, most universities have taken over the operation of clerical departments of different majors. This form of education allows young women to pursue higher education without compromising child care and other family responsibilities. I would like to take this opportunity to quote President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's speech to the Senate Oliy Majlis in June 2019: "Then it became our focus. Normally, we respect a woman first and foremost as a mother, as the custodian of the family. Of course, that's true. But

today every woman should not only be an observer, but also an active and active participant in the democratic changes underway in the country.”

On the same day, at the invitation of the President, for the first time in the country's history, a woman Tanzila Norbaeva was elected as the President of the Senate. It is known that Ms. Norbaeva used to hold the position of Deputy Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chairman of the Committee of Women of Uzbekistan. In order to further improve the legal framework for the protection and promotion of women's rights in Uzbekistan, in September 2019, the law "On ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men" and the law "Protection of protection of women against oppression and violence "was adopted. “Have been adopted. The law applies to virtually all United Nations agencies, including the United Nations Development Program, United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), High Level Office of the United Nations. The United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime, and the International Organization for Migration have commented on both laws. Regarding institutional measures for gender equality, a new committee on women and gender equality was established in the Oliy Majlis Senate of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the aim of harmonizing international law standards to ensure women's rights and the elimination of all forms of discrimination. In addition, the Republican Violence Victims' Rehabilitation and Adaptation Center, the Center for Suicide Prevention and the Center for Women Entrepreneurs, State Family, and new structures such as a scientific research center study and practice were established. An important aspect is that all these newly established institutional mechanisms together with the Uzbek Women's Committee will become a single integrated mechanism for the elimination of discrimination against women, gender equality and women under the United Nations Convention.

Considering educational opportunities, vocational training and selfdevelopment as a crucial factor in empowering and improving the wellbeing of women, the right to education in a country is equal for all citizens. This is guaranteed by the Constitution

of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 41). Equal rights of women and men to education The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education", and on physical development and sports the Law "On Physical Culture and Sports" (2nd article). In order to further expand the participation of women in the decisionmaking process, on March 2, 1995, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed a decree "On measures to enhance the role of women in the state and social construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan." of May 25, 2004 "On additional measures to support the activities of the Women`s Committee of Uzbekistan" and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers on these issues. Equality between men and women is enshrined in the main law of our country the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, article 46 of which says: "Women and men have equal rights." The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan guarantees everyone the full range of personal, social, political, cultural and economic rights enshrined in the International Convention on Human Rights. Our Constitution respects the inviolability of all person`s rights and freedoms, and no one has the right to restrict them. Since the early days of independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan has upheld democratic principles and adhered to about 70 fundamental international instruments in the field of human rights. These are the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Violence against Women, the Millennium Development Goals and others. It should be noted that the adopted normative and practical documents as well as practical measures represent an important step forward in the field of gender policy in Uzbekistan and are fully compliant with standards, legal rules and regulations. international practice, some of which are based on United Nations recommendations on rights. body part. In particular, it is important to pass legislation protecting women against oppression and violence. The law was passed after years of discussion. The law provides a framework to protect women by assisting victims of domestic violence, providing them with shelter, hotlines and mandatory prosecutions for crimes not only physical but psychologically or economically. In particular, such measures have long been recommended by the UN

Human Rights Office. Significant changes have taken place in the area of monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of gender policies due to the introduction of 54 additional gender indicators on the website www.uality.stat.uz. At the same time, it is necessary to carry out regular and consistent work in this direction. Here it is not only the directives adopted that are important that matter, but also their conformity with international obligations and standards, as well as their prompt and accurate implementation in practice.

CONCLUSION

In this sense, there is a need to work in unison to ensure the full and effective participation of women at all levels in decision-making in political, economic and social life. Therefore, there are plans to adopt roadmaps to ensure the enforcement of laws on ensuring equal rights and opportunities for women and men and legislation on the protection of women against oppression and violence. There are also plans to adopt a national strategy on gender equality. United Nations agencies stand ready to continue to assist on issues of gender equality and non-discrimination, including the planning, development and implementation of special instruments, as well as the development of special provisions for new criminal, procedural and executive codes. It is also important to ensure that legislation requires gender expertise so that documents passed at one level or another are uniform for men and women. In addition to business incubators, measures should be taken to encourage women's participation in education and science, and to involve them in science and technology through the establishment of STEM (department) laboratories. science, technology, engineering, math). This will help increase employment for women and improve their competitiveness in the modern labor market. Measures taken should cover all regions of the country and all women. In particular, special attention should be paid to the status of women in all forms of discrimination, taking into account the principles of the United Nations 2030 Global Agenda for Sustainable Development, in particular "no" rule. one is left behind. "These include women in rural areas of the country, ethnic minorities, people with disabilities, women with HIV/AIDS, women

in prisons and detention facilities (including prisons, schools, and prisons). boarding houses, retirement homes and mental hospitals), human rights defenders, Currently, within the framework of the cooperation of UN agencies in Uzbekistan, a special group on gender issues has been established, consisting of representatives of most UN agencies. For example, recommendations for the above laws remained part of the team's work throughout the project. In this group's example, UN agencies are always available to help in the development of other laws. In addition, the conference included a video, a video clinic, a legal clinic under the Uzbek Women's Committee, as well as several awareness-raising activities on women's issues of various forms. . In this regard, we actively cooperate with the Center for Development Strategy and other NGOs. In return, the United Nations team in Uzbekistan will continue to fully support the country to ensure gender equality within the framework of the Sustainable Development Cooperation Agenda for 2021-2025, which is currently being developed in consultation with the United Nations. of all national partners and other stakeholders. Deputy Chairperson of the “Oila” Center under the Cabinet of Ministers, Ms. Gulnara Ishankhanova states, “The new law is an ‘eye opener’ for everybody, including the state, as it affirms that the state should not tolerate discrimination against women, even if it is founded on deeply engrained stereotypes. This law will prompt the state to evaluate each situation from a gender point of view, from hiring for jobs, improving higher education opportunities for women to resolving family disputes.”

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PYSCHOLOGY

Features of economic socialization of women

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Abstract: This thesis provides analyzes of economic and psychological issues to ensure the active participation of women in society in the framework of reforms in Uzbekistan.

Key words: gender, society, woman, family, economic socialization, entrepreneurship.

Due to the rise of the protectionist policy in developed countries around the world, the demographic transformation of market relations, the irrationality of business subjects in relation to the requirements of the market economy, and the influence of such situations as gender inequality in them on the economic development of society, it is becoming more urgent to pay special attention to the territorial and gender issues of economic socialization of a person who is a subject of market relations. Therefore, Resolution No. 70, signed by the UN General Assembly at the "Summit on Sustainable Development" held in September 2015, as well as the goal of the UN Global Agenda until 2030 "Organizing systematic work on the consistent implementation of sustainable development goals" in connection with the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 83 of February 21, 2022 "On additional measures to accelerate the implementation of national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development until 2030" was signed [1].

In addition, within the framework of the implementation of the Fifth Sustainable Development Goal in the Republic of Uzbekistan, nine tasks related to ensuring gender equality and expanding the rights and opportunities of all women were developed [1]. In accordance with the objectives of the fifth goal (Gender equality), by 2030 it is necessary to eliminate all forms of discrimination against all women, to ensure the full and effective participation of women and equal opportunities for leadership at all levels of decision-making in political, economic and social life. In

accordance with the signed legal documents, all state bodies and organizations, institutions, as well as public organizations of state significance are responsible for the fulfillment of these tasks.

Therefore, in our country, ensuring all conditions for women to fully realize their limited opportunities has been raised to the level of state policy. In the end, a number of legal documents were signed in Uzbekistan, including presidential decrees and decisions on ensuring women's rights, in particular, on gender equality and protecting women from violence and oppression, and on strengthening the status of women's entrepreneurship development.

Practical activity in this regard, we, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on March 7, 2019 on measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship" PD-4235 [2] and based on this decision, We can witness the activities of the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan, because any gender equality is a factor of effective economic and social development.

Therefore, experts in the field, in addition to business incubators, are conducting practical actions on the need to encourage women in the field of education and science, as well as to attract them to the field of natural and technical sciences by creating STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) laboratories. The task is significant in that it is aimed at expanding programs that support women in realizing their rights and interests in the socio-economic sphere. This, in turn, improves the economic socialization of women, helps to increase their employment and competitiveness in the modern labor market conjuncture [5].

In our opinion, the successful socialization of a person is a process related to his activity in various spheres of social life, his readiness to meet social demands and requirements. In the process of child development, a person receives information about socially acceptable situations for men and women, prepares to fulfill their respective gender roles, i.e., undergoes gender socialization, which is one of the types of socialization.

Gender socialization is a process that occurs periodically throughout a person's life. Also, gender socialization reflects the changing conditions of society and the experience gained by the individual, and it is the material that shows the culture that forms the basis for the formation of gender in the course of a short period of time, as well as the system of knowledge about masculinity and femininity that is reduced by the individual during childhood and adolescence.

Gender stereotypes, based on society's perceptions of gender differences, have a serious impact on a person's abilities and qualities such as intelligence, rich intellectual potential, compatibility and impressiveness, aggressiveness, speech skills, empathy, emotionality, altruism, etc. In turn, in scientific sources, gender stereotypes are divided into the following groups:

- "masculinity-femininity" normative ideas about somatic, mental, behavioral characteristics characteristic of men and women;
- separation of family and professional roles (the main social roles for women are family - mother, housewife; for men - professionalism);
- the content of work (for women, this is the sphere of expressive activity, where the main thing is the performing and (or) service nature of work; and for men, as an instrumental sphere, where creative, constructive, leading work plays the main role) [3].

A well-known scientist A.V. According to Mudrik, at each stage of socialization, including gender differences, a person solves three tasks depending on age:

- "natural and cultural" (knowing how to satisfy the body; reducing the symbols of etiquette, kinesthetic language elements, realizing physical development and the ability to change attitudes and lifestyle depending on sexual orientation, healthy lifestyle, gender, age and individual abilities);
- "socio-cultural" (cognitive, moral, value-semantic - determined by certain socio-cultural conditions);
- "social-psychological" (self-awareness, self-determination, self-awareness of a person and self-affirmation) [4].

To sum up, firstly, successful socialization of the individual is ensured by the ability to change the directions of low values in the person, the ability to find a balance between their values and role requirements, and the ability to focus not on specific requirements, but on the understanding of universal moral values.

Secondly, cognitive (system of knowledge and ideas about existing gender roles, about yourself as a representative of a certain gender, about your image in front of people, etc.); motivational and (or) relational (internal desires to perform, accept or reject the gender role of the minority sex, attitude to the role of the other sex); It is possible to study economic socialization from a gender perspective, distinguishing the criteria of gender socialization in the form of behavior (gender stereotypes of behavior).

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Аннотация. Ҳозирда ўқитувчи ва ота-оналар учун бошланғич синф ўқувчилари таълим-тарбиясига қўйиладиган давлат талаблари яратилиб, амалиётда қўлланмоқда. Давлат мактабгача таълим ташкилотлари, хусусийлаштирилган мактабгача таълим ташкилотлари, турли мактабга тайёрлов марказларида болаларни мактабга тайёрлаш ишлари олиб боришмоқда. Шу нуқтаи назардан, ушбу мақолада бошланғич синф ўқувчилари ривожланиш ва дастлабки билим олиши тўғрисидаги ҳар бир оила ва жамият билиши зарур бўлган муҳим тавсиялар баён этилган.

Таянч сўз ва иборалар: компетент, интеграция, адаптация, ижтимоий муҳит, жамият, таълим тарбия, меҳнатсевар.

Социально-психологическая деятельность, осуществляемая с учащимся начальных классов

Абстрактный. В настоящее время создаются и реализуются на практике государственные требования к обучению учащихся начальных классов для учителей и родителей. Подготовка детей к школе осуществляется в государственных организациях дошкольного образования, частных организациях дошкольного образования, различных центрах подготовки к школе. В этом контексте в этой статье представлены важные рекомендации, которые каждая семья и сообщество должны знать о развитии и раннем обучении учащихся начальной школы.

Ключевые слова и фразы: компетентный, интеграция, адаптация, социальная среда, общество, образование, трудолюбие.

Social-psychological activity carried out with primary class students

Abstract. Currently, state requirements for the education of primary school students for teachers and parents are being created and put into practice. Children are being prepared for school in state preschool education organizations, privatized preschool

education organizations, various school preparation centers. In this context, this article presents important recommendations that every family and community should know about the development and early learning of elementary school students.

Key words and phrases: competence, integration, adaptation, social environment, society, education, hard work.

Дунёда болаларни мактабга моллаштириш, масъулиятлиликни ривожлантириш муаммосини аниқлаш ҳамда шахс маъсулиятини шакллантиришни такомиллаштириш бўйича илмий изланишлар олиб борилмоқда. Бу борада, жумладан, шахсга йўналтирилган таълим стратегияси талаблари ва компетенциявий ёндашув асосида бошланғич синф ўқувчиларини фаолиятлар интеграцияси жараёнида масъулиятлиликни шакллантиришнинг самарали шакллари ва усулларини жорий этиш, бошланғич синф ўқитувчиларининг инновацион фаолияти кўлами даражасини кенгайтириш, уларнинг касбий компетентлигини ривожлантириш масалаларига катта эътибор қаратилмоқда.

Республикамизда эрта болалик ёшидан бошлаб, атрофдагиларга, жамиятга, табиатга ва ўз фаолиятига масъулиятли муносабатни шакллантириш ва шу асосда ёш авлод маънавиятини бойитишга сўнгги йилларда алоҳида эътибор қаратиб келинмоқда. “Ёш авлоднинг ўқишга бўлган қизиқишини янада кучайтириш, китобхонларни маънавий ва моддий рағбатлантириш, фаол китобхонлар сафини кенгайтиришни назарда тутди”⁵. Ушбу вазифалардан келиб чиқган ҳолда республикамизда 6-7 ёшли болаларни мажбурий мактабга тайёрлов жараёнига қамраб олиш, эрта болалик давридан китобхонлик кўникмаларини шакллантириш борасида амалга оширилаётган тадқиқот ишлари муҳим илмий-амалий аҳамият касб этади.

⁵ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2020 йил 14 декабрдаги “2020-2025-йилларда китобхонлик маданиятини ривожлантириш ва қўллаб-қувватлаш миллий дастурини тасдиқлаш тўғрисида” ВМҚ-781 сон қарори. <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5160827#-5162595>

Ҳозирги кунда мактабгача ёшдаги болаларни мактабга тайёрлаш янги омилларни излаш, топиш, тажриба-синовлардан ўтказиш асосида амалга ошириш заруриятини талаб этмоқда. Мактабга тайёрлашда болаларнинг руҳий тайёргарлиги, жисмонан соғлом бўлиши, мулоқотга кира олиши, сўз бойлигини (захирасини) бойитиш, бошланғич элементар математик тушунчаларга эга бўлиши, ёзишга бошланғич тайёргарлик, айрим сўзлар тўғрисида тасаввурларни билиши муҳим роль ўйнайди. Айниқса 6-7 ёшли боланинг ахборотга эҳтиёжи кўпдир. Бу борада таълим муассасаларида тарбияланаётган барча болалар учун ижтимоий адаптация муаммоси муҳим аҳамиятга эга. Ҳозирги вақтда боланинг кўникиш имкониятларини ошириш, унинг ижтимоий алоқаларини кенгайтириш бола шахсининг шаклланиши учун ниҳоятда катта аҳамият касб этмоқда.

Адаптация (лот. adaptatio — мослашув) – организмнинг, масалан, сезги аъзоларининг атроф-муҳит шароитларига мослашиши, кўникиши¹. Бошқача айтганда, организмнинг ташқи муҳит билан адекват алоқалари шаклланиши хусусиятидир.

А.В.Петровский концепциясида берилган изоҳда мослашув алоҳида шахсий ривожланишининг табиатига боғлиқ бўлган шахсининг шаклланишидаги босқич ҳисобланади.⁶

Бола туғма юриш-туриш шаклларига эга эмас ва у ижтимоий муҳитда ривожлана бориб уч асосий компонентни: худуд (нарса-предметлар, улардан фойдаланиш воситалари), вақт (кундалик тартиб) ва муомала шаклларини ўзлаштиради. Демак, бола туғилишдан оқ унинг фаоллиги «бола-катталар» муносабатлари ичида тартибга солинади.

Янги шароитга қийинчилик билан кўникадиган болаларда мослашиш жараёни йил давомида кечиши мумкин, муваффақиятли мослашиш белгилари эса нотўғри белгилар билан алмаштирилади. Мактабда ва уйда ўқув жараёнини

⁶ Петровский А.В.. Психолого-педагогический словарь / Сост. Рапацевич Е.С. – Минск: «Соврем. слово», 2006. – 928 с

моҳирлик билан ташкил этиш билан барча қийинчиликларни охир -оқибат бартараф этиш мумкин.

Психолог болаларнинг мактабга кўникиш даражасини аниқлаши учун куйидаги таснифга таяниши лозим:

Мослашувнинг юқори даражаси. Биринчи синф ўқувчиси мактабга ижобий муносабатда, талабларни етарли даражада қабул қилади; ўқув материални осонгина ўрганади; ўқув дастур материални чуқур ва тўлиқ ўзлаштиради; мураккаб вазифаларни ҳал қилади; меҳнатсевар, ўқитувчининг кўрсатмаларини, тушунтиришларини диққат билан тинглайди; мустақил илмий ишларга катта қизиқиш кўрсатади, барча дарсларга тайёрланади; жамоат топшириқларини бажонидил, виждонан бажаради; синфда қулай мақомни эгаллайди.

Мослашувнинг ўртача даражаси. Биринчи синф ўқувчиси мактабга ижобий муносабатда, унинг иштироки салбий ҳис-туйғуларга олиб келмайди; ўқитувчи ўқув материални батафсил ва аниқ баён қилса, ўқув материални тушунади; ўқув дастурларининг асосий мазмунини ўзлаштиради, одатдаги вазифаларни мустақил равишда ҳал қилади; катталарнинг вазифалари, топшириқлари, кўрсатмаларини бажаришда диққатли ва эътиборли, аммо унинг назорати остида; фақат у учун қизиқарли нарса бўлганда дарсларга тайёргарлик кўради ва деярли ҳар доим уй вазифасини бажаради; жамоат топшириқларини виждонан бажаради; кўплаб синфдошлар билан дўстдир.

Мослашувнинг паст даражаси. Биринчи синф ўқувчисиди мактабга салбий ёки бефарқ муносабат бор; саломатлигидаги шикоятлар кам эмас; ғамгин кайфият ҳукмронлик қилади; интизомини бузилиши кузатилади; ўқувчи мустақил иш бажаришда қийланади; мустақил таълим вазифаларни бажаришда қизиқиши паст; у тартибсиз дарс тайёрлайди, доим назорат қилиш керак, таълим жараёнида вазифаларни бажаришда ўқитувчи ва ота -оналардан ёрдами бериш талаб этилади; назорат остида жамоат топшириқларини

бажаради, жуда хоҳишсиз, пассив, яқин дўстлари йўқ, синфдошларнинг фақат бир қисминигина исмини билади.

Мактабгача таълим муассасалари ва умумий ўрта таълим мактаблари давлат талабалари асосида мактабгача таълим муассасалари тарбиячи-педагоглари ва таълим муассасаси психололар томонидан ижтимоий-гигиеник жиҳатларга бағишланган ишларда мактабгача ёшдаги болаларнинг адаптация даврида бир қатор муҳим параметрларни, яъни касалланиш, юриштириш, руҳий ривожланишидаги ўзгаришларни эътиборга олиш кераклиги таъкидланади.

Кичик ўқувчиларни мактабга мослашишининг руҳий-педагогик муаммоларини ўрганиш бўйича бизнинг тадқиқот ишларини якунини умумлаштириб, биз томондан бир қатор тавсиялар ишлаб чиқилган, унинг мақсади мактаб таълимига биринчи синфларни мослашишининг қулай кечишини таъминловчи психологик-педагогик шароитларини яратиш саналади.

Мактабга тайёргарлик кўпинча биринчи синф дастурини олдинроқ ўрганиш сифатида қаралади. Бундай ҳолда, мактабгача ва бошланғич таълим ёши ўртасидаги узлуксизлик бўлажак ўқувчида янги таълим фаолиятини амалга ошириш учун зарур бўлган фазилатларни шакллантирганлиги, унинг шарт-шароитлари шаклланганлиги билан эмас, балки маълум билимларнинг мавжудлиги ёки йўқлиги билан белгиланади. Бироқ, психологлар ва ўқитувчилар томонидан олиб борилган кўплаб тадқиқотлар шуни кўрсатадики, билимларнинг мавжудлиги ўз-ўзидан-таълим муваффақиятини белгиламайди, балки боланинг билимларни мустақил равишда қандай эгаллаши ва амалда қўллашни билиши муҳимроқдир. Бошланғич таълим босқичига бола тайёргарлигининг асосий мақсади мактабгача ёшдаги болада таълим фаолиятини ўзлаштириш учун зарур бўлган қуйдаги фазилатларни шакллантириш керак: қизиқувчанлик, ташаббускорлик, мустақиллик, ўзбошимчалик, боланинг ўзини ижодий намоён этиши ва бошқалар. Айни пайтда, шуни ёдда тутиш керакки, боғча ва бошланғич таълим босқичлари

Ўртасидаги узлуксизлик фақат болаларни ўрганишга тайёрлаш деб тушунилмаслиги керак. Келажакдаги шахснинг энг муҳим хусусиятлари шакллантирилган мактабгача ёшдаги боланинг ички қийматини сақлашни таъминлаш муҳимдир. Бўлажак ўқувчининг мактабга муваффақиятли мослашиши учун зарур бўлгани жтимоий кўникмаларни шакллантириш керак. Ягона ривожланаётган дунё - мактабгача ва бошланғич таълимни ташкил этишга интилиш керак.

Биз мослашиш даврининг қуйидаги вазифаларини ажратамиз:

Болада ўқувчининг ички позицияси шаклланишида ёрдам бериш;

Саломатликни мустаҳкамловчи фаолият;

Ўқув мотивациясини шакллантириш;

Баҳо, ўзини баҳолаш тушунчалари билан танишиш;

Ҳал қилувчанлик, ўзига ишонч, очиклик каби ички сифатларни ривожлантириш;

Ота-оналарни янги вазифа- ўқувчи ота-оналигига тайёрлаш.

Мослашиш жараёнини психологик-педагогик масала сифатида кўриб чиқиб ва биринчи синф ўқувчисининг руҳий-педагогик хусусиятлари билан боғлиқ 6-8 ёшдаги болаларнинг мактаб таълимига муваффақиятли мослашишининг бир қатор шароитларини ажратиш мумкин:

Болалар боғчасига бориш.

Машғулотларда спорт машқларидан фойдаланиш.

Ўзгаришлар вақтида тоза ҳавода фаол ҳордиқ.

Ўқишнинг санитар-гигиеник шартлари мувофиқлиги.

Дарс вақтини қисқартириш.

Мураккаблигига кўра дарсларни алмаштириш.

Биринчи синфдагиларга фаол ғамхўрликни ташкил қилиш.

Мактаб мутахассисларининг тўғри ташкил қилинган иши: психолог, тиббиёт ходими, ўқитувчиларнинг турли ташхис шаклларини ўз вақтида ўтказиш ва тавсиялар бериш бўйича.

Барча ўқув жараёнларига ўқитувчининг раҳбарлиги ва ўқувчилар билан муносабатда унинг лаёқатлилиги.

Ўқувчининг янги мақомига оиланинг ижобий муносабати.

Синф раҳбарига тавсиялар.

Биринчи синф раҳбарига қуйидаги болалар билан тўғри ишни ташкил қилиш тавсия этилади:

Ўзлаштириш қобилияти ёмон ривожланган, у мактабга интеллектуал тайёргарликнинг асосий мезони саналади;

Ўз фаолиятини қоидаларга бўйсундира олмайдиган, юқори ҳаракат фаоллигига эга;

талабларнинг белгиланган тизимига йўналтирилмаган;

сўзловчини диққат билан тингламайдиган ва оғзаки шаклда берилган машқни қийинчиликсиз бажара олмайдиган.

Синф раҳбари қуйидаги ишларни бажариши зарур:

ўқув мотивларини шакллантириш устида;

болаларнинг ақлий қизиқишларини ривожлантириш устида;

интеллектуал фаоллик ҳамда янги билим, малака ва кўникмаларни ўзлаштиришга бўлган эҳтиёжларни рағбатлантириш;

ўқувчининг ички позициясини шакллантириш зарур.

Ўқитувчи қуйидагиларга алоҳида эътибор қаратиши керак:

- диққатни ривожлантириш (эътибор, барқарорлик, тақсимот, ўзгартириш каби сифатлар);
- Болада намуна ва кўрсатма бўйича ишлаш кўникмасини шакллантириш;
- Боланинг ўз фаолиятини режалаштириш ва назоратни амалга ошириш кўникмаси;
- мустақил фаолият кўникмаларини ривожлантириш;
- ўз фаолиятини топшириқни бажаришга ажратилган вақтга бўйсундириш кўникмасини ривожлантириш.

Биринчи синф ўқитувчисига тавсиялар:

Болага етарлича эътибор қаратинг. Унинг саволларини жавобсиз қолдирманг ва у сизнинг ёрдамингизга муҳтож бўлганда уни рад қилманг.

Ҳар бир бола ўзининг индивидуал хусусиятларига эга, уларни ҳисобга олинг ва бошқалар билан таққосламанг.

Синфдан ташқари фаолиятда иштирок этинг, бошқа болаларнинг ота-оналари билан мулоқот қилинг. Сиз ҳам жамоанинг бир қисми ва бола учун барча нарсада намуна саналасиз.

Болага нафақат мактабдаги хулқ меъёрлари тўғрисида билим бериш балки у маълум ахлоқий-маънавий сифатларни ривожлантиришга қодир бўлган тарбияни бериш керак.

Боланинг кун тартибини ташкил қилиш, овқатланишнинг тўғри тартибига риоя қилиш керак. Болани толиқишдан сақланг.

У ниманидир вақтида бажарганда болани мақтанг, агар у ниманидир бажара олмаса койиманг, хатоларни тузатишга ва пайдо бўлган қийинчиликларни бартараф қилишга ёрдам беринг.

Бола учун унинг топшириқларини бажарманг. Бу унга ўз кучига ишончни мустаҳкамлайди ва ўз мажбуриятларини тушуниш ва бажаришга хизмат қилади.

Фарзандингиз синф раҳбари билан доимий алоқани сақланг. Унинг ўзлаштириши, синфдошлари билан муносабатлари ва хулқига қизиқинг.

Уйда қулай муҳитни таъминланг. Ўқиш боши болада стрессга олиб келиши мумкин, шунинг учун уй муҳитининг хотиржамлиги ва барқарорлиги мактабдаги муаммоларни самарали ҳал қилишга ёрдам беради.

1. Ўқишга боланинг қизиқишларини қўллаб-қувватланг ва ривожлантиринг.

2. Мактаб ташвишларига хотиржам муносабатда бўлинг ва пайдо бўлган масалалардан хавотир олманг. Сизнинг хотиржамлик ва ишончингиз болага мактабдан қўрқиш керак эмаслигига ишонч беради.

3. Боланинг руҳий ва жисмоний зўриқишларини бартараф қилинг. Узвий алоқани доимо сақланг.
4. Уй вазифасини тезкор бажаришга болани мажбур қилинг. Уйга қайтганда болага дам олиш имконини беринг. Уй вазифасини бажариш вақтида танаффуслар қилинг.
5. Боланинг манфаатлар доираси ва фаолиятини туташтирманг, бола мустақил қила оладиган машғулот билан шуғуллантиринг.
6. Болага ижодий фаолиятда тасаввур қилиш имконини беринг (расм чизиш, ясаш). Бундай фаолиятда эътибор, руҳий кўма, муваффақиятни таъминланг.
7. Тезкор муваффақиятни талаб қилманг ва ўзингиз ҳамда бола учун эталон яратманг. Мактаб муваффақиятларидан ўз ташвишингизни болага кўрсатманг.

Юқоридаги тавсияларни амалий фаолиятда ўқитувчи ва ота-оналар ҳамкорликда амалга оширсалар, боланинг мактабга мослашишига, ижтимоийлашуви ва маънавий-жисмоний ривожланишига ижобий таъсир этади. Натижада ўзимиз орзу қилган соғлом болаларни тарбиялаб, соғлом жамият қуришга ўз ҳиссамизни қўшган бўламиз.

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STATE AND LAW

Basic guarantees of women's social rights: legal and material provision

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Abstract: The article analyzes the constitutional guarantees of women's social rights. The scientific views of scientists on the concept of guarantees of women's social rights are analyzed.

Key words: women's rights, social rights, material guarantee, legal guarantee, right to work, freedom of choice of profession, right to access medical services, right to social security, pregnancy, equal rights, maternity protection, social discrimination, decree, legal guarantee, equality.

The prestige of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the international arena largely depends on the provision of human rights, especially the rights of women.

The Republic of Uzbekistan joined the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women adopted in New York on December 18, 1979. This Convention states that all necessary measures should be implemented for women to have equal rights with men in the field of social activity. The provisions on women's rights stated in this Convention and international legal documents on human rights are reflected in the Constitution and legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Despite the above, there is a need to improve the provision of women's social rights. Therefore, women's right to work, right to rest, right to health care, right to maternity care, right to social security and right to housing need to be guaranteed by the state. In particular, the issue of social protection of women who have fallen into a serious social situation, need help, have low income, lost their breadwinner, divorced, disabled, are raising their children alone, need housing, and are unemployed is an urgent and priority task at the level of state social policy [3].

The set of tools, methods and conditions that help the state to ensure the realization of the social rights and freedoms of women enshrined in the Constitution and laws is expressed in the concept of guarantee.

Legal guarantees are the means, methods and conditions that ensure the realization of women's rights and freedoms.

Material guarantee is the legal basis for ensuring women's material rights and recovering damage caused as a result of violation of their material rights [4].

Some authors say that legal guarantees, Academician A. Saidov, - understand the system of broad institutions and material and procedural substances, they believe that the system of ensuring subjective rights can work only through legal guarantees consisting of law-establishing and law-restoring norms [1].

In order to ensure gender equality in social relations, governments around the world have introduced legal and material guarantees to women from the moment of pregnancy to protect motherhood. Also, according to D. Atajanova, "pregnancy" is not only a medical category, but it is also considered as an important legal category for the fields of labor law, social security law, administrative law, and criminal law [2].

In particular, the recommendation nature of the list of areas and professions limited to women's work means that they can conclude an employment contract with the employer if they want to work in the positions listed in this list. This guarantees equal rights for women in ensuring labor rights. However, based on the physiological characteristics of women's bodies, taking into account their reproductive function, in order to protect motherhood, it is appropriate to prohibit them from working in areas with unfavorable working conditions [5]. In addition, the employment of mothers with disabled children under the age of sixteen in such fields and professions may create a risk of disability if adequate labor protection is not provided. However, the fact that such a ban is advisory in nature means positive discrimination. Based on this, it is necessary to make amendments to the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan to introduce additional labor protection in the fields and professions in which women can work, and to prohibit the work of women who are pregnant and have children under the age of three, as well as those who have disabled children under the age of sixteen [6].

According to the Labor Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan, pregnant women, women with children under the age of three, and persons sent to work at the expense of the minimum number of jobs for the enterprise do not have a preliminary test. However, for girls under the age of eighteen who want to work, the "preliminary test" is a kind of bureaucratic hurdle. In particular, our labor legislation does not specify restrictions on setting preliminary tests for minors. Based on this, the inclusion of a preliminary test clause in the employment contract may cause social discrimination against young, inexperienced employees whose qualifications are clearly insufficient. The Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan also includes the category of "persons sent to work at the expense of the minimum number of jobs specified for the enterprise" within the scope of employees who do not have a preliminary test. This category of employees also includes women with disabilities. However, it will be possible to apply the initial test to persons with disabilities who are admitted to workplaces that are not organized at the expense of minimum workplaces[6].

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ECONOMY

Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришда саноат корхоналарининг ўрни

Нарзикулова Шахноза Хошимжоновна –

Самарканд шаҳар 17 -мактабгача таълим ташкилоти директори

Аннотация ушбу мақолда хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришда саноат корхоналарининг миллий иқтисодиётни ривождаги ўрни ўрганилган. Ўзбекистон Республикасида саноат корхоналари таркибининг такомиллашуви, озиқ-овқат саноати ривожланишига, аҳоли бандлигини таъминланишига ва ишлаб чиқаришни кўпайтиришга боғлиқ эканлигига алоҳида урғу берилган.

Калит сўзлар: стратегия, рақобат, инновацион хизматлар, тадбиркорлик, хизмат, аҳоли бандлиги, турмуш даражаси.

Аннотация В данной статье исследуется роль промышленных предприятий в развитии народного хозяйства в развитии пищевой промышленности. Совершенствование структуры промышленных предприятий Республики Узбекистан зависит от развития пищевой промышленности, обеспечения занятости и увеличения производства.

Ключевые слова: стратегия, конкуренция, инновационные услуги, предпринимательство, сервис, занятость населения, уровень жизни.

Annotation This article examines the role of industrial enterprises in the development of the national economy in the development of the food industry. Improving the structure of industrial enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan depends on the development of the food industry, providing employment and increasing production.

Key words: strategy, competition, innovative services, entrepreneurship, service, employment, standard of living.

Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантириш, мамлакатимиз иқтисодиётининг устувор йўналишларидандир. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 7 февралдаги фармони билан 2017-2021 йилларда Ўзбекистон Республикасини ривожлантиришнинг бешта устувор йўналиш бўйича

ҳаракатлар стратегия қабул қилинди. Ушбу ҳужжат аслида жамиятнинг барча жабҳаларида тизимли ислоҳотлар учун «йўл харитаси» га айланди. Бугунги кунда сервис ва хизматлар соҳаси, иқтисодиётнинг энг муҳим тармоқларидан ҳисобланади. Давлат томонидан ушбу соҳани қўллаб-қувватлаш сиёсатини амалга ошириш, мамлакатимизда хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришни рағбатлантириш эвазига ижобий натижаларга эришилмоқда. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг «2016-2020 йилларда хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантириш дастури тўғрисида» ги қарори Ўзбекистоннинг хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасини ривожлантиришнинг устувор йўналиш ва вазифаларини, шу жумладан:

- хизматларни ривожлантириш ҳисобига ялпи ички маҳсулотни кўпайтириш, унинг иқтисодиётдаги улушини 48,7 фоизга етказиш;
- 2020 йилга келиб, қишлоқ жойларида хизматларнинг 1,8 баробар ўсиши;
- сервис соҳасида жадал ривожланиш учун шарт-шароитларни яратиш, муҳандислик, коммуникация, автомобиль ва транспорт инфратузилмасини ривожлантириш, тармоқларда замонавий ахборот-коммуникация технологияларини жорий этиш ҳисобига таркибий ўзгаришларни амалга ошириш;
- рақобат муҳитини шакллантириш, кичик ва хусусий тадбиркорлик субъектларини ривожлантиришга кўмаклашиш;
- турли хил инновацион хизматларни, янги алоқа объектларини кенгайтириш;
- аҳолининг телекоммуникация тармоғига техник имкониятларини таъминлаш, уларнинг асосида юқори сифатли хизматлар кўрсатиш, рақамли телефон алоқа ва телевидение тизимларига ўтишни таъминлаш, республика иқтисодиётида алоқа ва ахборотлаштириш хизматларининг улушини 2020 йилгача 2,5 фоизга ошириш;
- замонавий электрон тўлов технологияларини жорий этиш билан молиявий хизматларни ривожлантириш;

- юқори технологияли тиббий хизматларни янада ривожлантириш.⁷

Хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаларини ҳар томонлама ривожлантиришда саноат корхоналарини барқарор ривожлантириш, аҳоли бандлигини таъминлаш ва аҳоли турмуш даражасини оширишнинг долзарб масаласи ҳисобланади.

Ҳозирги кунда ривожланган ва ривожланаётган мамлакатлар иқтисодий ўсишга таъсир кўрсатиш учун саноат корхоналарида хизматлар соҳасини жадал ривожлантиришни муҳим вазифа сифатида белгилаб олган. Саноат корхоналарида хизмат кўрсатиш соҳаси аҳолининг барча қатламларини қамраб олади ва деярли барча ижтимоий-иқтисодий жараёнларга таъсир кўрсатади. Кейинги йилларида мамлакатимиздаги юзага келаётган таркибий ўзгаришлар ва иқтисодиётни диверсификация қилиш, аҳоли бандлиги, даромадлари ва турмуш даражасини оширишнинг энг муҳим омилларидан бири сифатида саноат корхоналарида хизмат кўрсатиш тизимини жадал ривожлантириш борасида ишлар олиб борилмоқда. Бу эса аҳолини хизмат кўрсатишга бўлган талабини ошишига олиб келади.

Саноат корхоналари бугунги кунда доимий ўзгарувчан бозор шароитида ишламоқда. Шу сабабли ҳам улар ўртасида мунтазам равишда рақобат муҳити юзага келиб туради. Янги рақобат муҳитининг пайдо бўлиши саноат корхоналари раҳбарлари, ишчи ходимларининг хизмат сифати ҳамда самарадорлигига кучли эътибор беришга мажбур қилади.

Шу жиҳатдан олиб қаралганда саноат корхоналари ҳозирда рақобат шароитига тезда мослашишлари билан бирга қўшимча хизмат турларини тақдим этиб туришлари шарт. Бунинг учун зарур бўлган муҳим шартлардан бири ушбу корхоналарда кўрсатиладиган хизматларнинг самарадорлиги ҳисобланади агар самарадорликка эришиш йўллари излаб топилса, уйлаймизки, хизматлар соҳаси ривожда саноат корхоналарининг ўрни муҳим аҳамият касб этади.

⁷ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 2016 йил 26 февралдаги 55 -сонли “2016-2020 йилларда хизмат кўрсатиш ва сервис соҳасини ривожлантириш дастури тўғрисида” ги қарори.

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